

Dimethyl Ether as an ignition improver for Hydrous Methanol Fuelled Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition (HCCI) Engine

Authors : M. Venkatesan, N. Shenbaga Vinayaga Moorthi, R. Karthikeyan and A. Manivannan

Abstract : This paper deals with experimental investigations of homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition (HCCI) engine using hydrous methanol as a primary fuel and Diethyl ether (DEE) as an ignition improver. In the present work a regular diesel engine has been modified to work as HCCI engine. The hydrous methanol is inducted and DEE is injected into a single cylinder engine. Hence, in the present investigation HydrousMethanol is used with 15% water content in HCCI engine and its performance and emission behavior is documented. Here, Diethyl ether (DEE) is used as an ignition improver and admitted along with Methanol fuel through separate fuel admission device. The auto-ignition of Methanol is enabled by DEE. The quantity of DEE varies with respect to the load. In this study, the experiments are conducted independently and the effect of the HydrousMethanol on the engine operating limit, heat release rate and exhaust emissions at different load conditions are investigated. The investigation also proves that the HydrousMethanol with DEE operation reduces the emission of NO_x and smoke to an extreme low level which is not possible by the direct injection CI engine. Thus the HydrousMethanol with 15% water content and DEE operate well in HCCI engine without any operational problem. Therefore, it is beneficial to use hydrous methanol-DEE HCCI mode while using hydrous methanol in internal Combustion Engines.

Keywords : Hydrous Methanol, Diethyl ether, Performance, Emission and Combustion

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